

Assessing the Causes of Conflict Between Host Communities and Industrial Organisations in the Niger Delta Region

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Abstract

The Niger Delta region of Nigeria, though richly endowed with petroleum resources, remains one of the most volatile and underdeveloped areas in the country. This study investigated the underlying causes of conflict between host communities and industrial organisations (Exxon Mobil and Chevron), the major oil multinationals operating in the region. Anchored on a mixed-methods research design, the study drew data from a structured questionnaire and in-depth interviews within selected communities in the Niger Delta. Findings revealed that environmental degradation, perceived inequities in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), lack of community involvement in decision-making, and weak government regulatory frameworks are significant drivers of conflict. The study further highlights the role of youth unemployment and cultural alienation in intensifying hostilities. While ExxonMobil and Chevron have initiated several CSR projects, community perceptions suggest these efforts are often inadequate or misaligned with local needs. The research concludes that sustainable peace and improved corporate-community relations require more inclusive engagement, responsive governance, and environmentally conscious practices. Recommendations are offered for policymakers, oil companies, and civil society actors to address the conflict's root causes and promote long-term stability in the Niger Delta.

Keywords: Causes, Conflict, Industrial Organisations, Exxon Mobil, Chevron, Niger Delta

Introduction

The Niger Delta region of Nigeria, rich in petroleum resources, has long been characterised by a complex web of socio-economic and environmental challenges, most notably the persistent conflict between host communities and multinational oil corporations. Among the most prominent of these corporations are Exxon Mobil and Chevron, whose operations have significantly shaped the landscape of oil exploration in the region. While these activities have contributed substantially to Nigeria's economy, they have also been accompanied by deep-rooted tensions and disputes, particularly with the indigenous communities that host these operations.

The causes of conflict between host communities and Chevron and Exxon Mobil are multifaceted, often rooted in issues of environmental degradation, inadequate Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), perceived marginalisation, lack of community engagement, and unmet developmental expectations. Oil spills, gas flaring, and land degradation have not only disrupted traditional livelihoods, especially fishing and farming, but have also fuelled grievances over compensation, employment opportunities, and infrastructural neglect. These tensions have sometimes escalated into protests, legal actions, sabotage of oil facilities, and broader insecurity in the region.

This study, therefore, sought to critically assess the underlying causes of the conflict between host communities and Chevron and Exxon Mobil in the Niger Delta. It aims to explore how historical, political, environmental, and socio-economic factors converge to influence the patterns and persistence of unrest. By identifying the key drivers of these hostilities, the research hopes to offer insight into potential pathways for sustainable conflict resolution, equitable community development, and improved corporate-community relations in Nigeria's oil-rich region.

Conflict between multinational oil companies and host communities in the Niger Delta has been widely explored in academic and policy literature, highlighting both structural and proximate causes. Scholars have argued that the discovery and exploitation of crude oil in the region since the late 1950s have led to environmental degradation, socioeconomic displacement, and deep-seated grievances (Obi, 2010; Okonta & Douglas, 2003). These conditions have fuelled prolonged resistance and, at times, violent confrontations between local communities and oil companies, such as ExxonMobil and Chevron.

A central theme in the literature is **environmental degradation**. Oil exploration activities, especially gas flaring, pipeline vandalism, and oil spills, have severely impacted agricultural land, fishing waters, and biodiversity (UNDP, 2006). As Omeje (2006) notes, ecological damage has disrupted the traditional livelihoods of local populations, creating economic marginalisation and a sense of injustice. ExxonMobil and Chevron, like other oil majors, have been accused of insufficient responsiveness to environmental concerns, often leading to host community resentment and protest (Ibaba, 2008).

Another major cause identified in the literature is the **lack of inclusive development and social infrastructure**. According to Akpan (2010), many host communities perceive oil companies as extractive entities that profit at the expense of local well-being. Despite various Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programmes by ExxonMobil and Chevron, many of these initiatives are seen as inadequate, poorly implemented, or not aligned with community needs (Nwankwo & Ifejika, 2011). This perception contributes to distrust, community agitation, and the breakdown of

corporate-community relations.

The issue of **political and governance failure** also features prominently in scholarly discourse. The federal government controls oil revenue and resource governance, often sidelining the direct needs and voices of host communities. As Watts (2004) asserts, this centralisation breeds feelings of exclusion and fuels ethno-regional conflicts. Multinational oil corporations operating under federal licences are often viewed as complicit in the marginalisation of local voices.

Youth unemployment and militancy are other dimensions of conflict causation. Ukeje (2001) and Ikelegbe (2005) highlight how frustrated and unemployed youths are easily mobilised to engage in protests, pipeline sabotage, and hostage-taking. These actions are not only expressions of discontent but also survival strategies in a region plagued by underdevelopment and inequality.

Despite several peace-building efforts, including Memoranda of Understanding (MOU), community development agreements, and joint task force security measures, the literature suggests that the absence of genuine dialogue, transparency, and participatory development continues to undermine sustainable peace (Aghalino, 2009; Nlerum, 2014).

In summary, the literature converges on the idea that the conflict between ExxonMobil, Chevron and host communities in the Niger Delta is a complex interplay of environmental, economic, political, and social factors. However, there remains a gap in understanding the localised experiences of specific communities in relation to ExxonMobil's and Chevron's operations, making further empirical investigation both relevant and necessary.

Despite decades of oil exploration and substantial revenue generation from the Niger Delta, host communities in the region continue to suffer from severe environmental degradation, underdevelopment, and socio-economic marginalisation. This paradox has given rise to persistent conflicts between local communities and multinational oil companies, particularly ExxonMobil and Chevron, two of the key players in the region. The hostilities manifest in forms ranging from peaceful protests and legal disputes to militancy, vandalism, and disruption of oil operations.

Although ExxonMobil and Chevron have implemented several Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives aimed at addressing community needs, many of these interventions are perceived as either inadequate, insincere, or poorly targeted. Compounding these are grievances over oil spills, gas flaring, inadequate compensation, exclusion from decision-making, and unemployment—factors that fuel community frustration and escalate tensions. The Nigerian government's centralised

control over oil resources and weak regulatory enforcement further exacerbate the situation, leaving host communities feeling alienated and powerless.

While previous studies have explored the broad causes of conflict in the Niger Delta, there is a limited focus on the specific dynamics of community-company relations involving ExxonMobil and Chevron. There is a knowledge gap regarding how localised factors, such as cultural expectations, communication practices, and historical grievances, shape the conflict landscape. Without a nuanced understanding of these causes, efforts toward conflict resolution, policy reforms, and sustainable corporate engagement are likely to remain ineffective.

This study, therefore, sought to assess the root causes and specific triggers of conflict between industrial companies and their host communities in the Niger Delta, with the aim of providing context-specific insights that can inform more sustainable approaches to peacebuilding, corporate responsibility, and community development in oil-producing regions.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study was to determine the management strategies adopted in curbing conflict among communities and oil companies in the Niger Delta region.

Research Questions

One research question was raised to guide the study: What are the causes of conflict between communities and oil companies in the Niger Delta region?

Research Method

This study adopted a **mixed-methods research design**, combining both qualitative and quantitative approaches. This design is suitable for exploring the complex and multidimensional nature of conflict by integrating statistical trends with personal and community narratives. The qualitative aspect provided in-depth insight into the perceptions and lived experiences of stakeholders, while the quantitative component helped to measure the prevalence and intensity of key conflict drivers. The study area is the Niger Delta region of Nigeria; specifically, Akwa Ibom and Delta states because of the presence of two large oil companies in the states. The population of this study consisted of the adult population of *Otunana* (host community of Chevron in Delta State) and *Ibeno* (host community of ExxonMobil in Akwa-Ibom State). The researcher believed that members of these communities were in a better position to supply dependable information to examine community development projects as a conflict management strategy among oil companies in the Niger Delta. Thus, following the 2006 population census, *Otunana* (Warri South LGA) has a population of 58,974 (NPC,

2006), while *Ibena* has a population of 38,539 (NPC, 2006).

Following the 3.5% standardised population growth estimate per annum, the population estimate of *Otunana* (Warri South LGA) by 2020 is 3.5% of 58,974, which is $0.035 \times 58,974$, resulting in 2,064. Because a 14-year projection (2006 to 2020) was made, 2,064 was multiplied by 14 (2064×14) to get the projected population growth of 28,896. To get the actual population in 2020 as projected from the year 2006, the projected population growth figure (28,896) was added to the *Otunana* (Warri South LGA) population figure of 2006 (58,974). Thus, the population estimate of *Otunana* (Warri South LGA) in 2020 is $28,896 + 58,974 = 87,870$. In line with this population projection estimate formula, the population of *Ibena*, Ibena local government area, by 2020 is 3.5% of 38,539, calculated as $0.035 \times 38,539$, resulting in 1,349. Because a 14-year projection (2006 to 2020) was made, 1,349 was multiplied by 14 (1349×14) to get the projected population growth of 18,886. To get the actual population in 2020 as projected from the year 2006, the projected population growth figure (18,886) was added to the population figure of 2006 (38,539). Thus, the population estimate of *Ibena*, Ibena local government area, in 2020 is $18,886 + 38,539 = 57,425$. Therefore, the target population for this study was 145,295, which is the 2020 projected adult population of *Otunana* (Warri South LGA) and *Ibena*, Ibena local government area, put together. The sample size of this study was 1,059 respondents. Ten respondents out of the sample size were selected purposively for an In-Depth Interview (IDI).

This study adopted the systematic random sampling method. Thus, following the natural clusters of layouts in *Otunana* and *Ibena* and their housing units, respondents were being picked at intervals of 5 housing units. At the end, 529 respondents were selected from *Otunana* and 530 respondents selected from *Ibena*. The essence of this variation was to ensure that the sample size of 1,059 was met for the quantitative part of the study. Questionnaire and In-depth Interview (IDI) guides were adopted as instruments for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions. The second instrument (IDI) was used to complement the questionnaire. The purpose was to employ a qualitative method which is known for exploring grey areas that are not made explicit in the questionnaire.

The researcher employed the services of three research assistants from the study area who assisted in administering and retrieving the questionnaire on completion by the respondents during the fieldwork. Out of 1,059 copies of the questionnaire administered, 860 copies were retrieved, giving a retrieval rate of 81 percent.

Data collected were properly checked to make sure all items in each of the questionnaires were responded to. Thereafter, responses were coded and analysed using appropriate statistical methods. Frequency distribution tables, percentages and charts were used to organise and present the quantitative data, while information obtained through qualitative data was thematically analysed, complementing the quantitative

data appropriately.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Distribution of respondents on the major causes of the conflicts

Causes of the conflicts	Frequency	Percentages
Environmental degradation by oil companies	275	32
Unjust and inadequate allotment of community projects by the oil company	168	19.5
Denying indigenes of job opportunities in the oil companies	182	21.2
Haphazard or lack of speedy completion of community development projects by the oil companies	130	15.1
Unrepentant youth militancy behaviours	105	12.2
Total	860	100.0

Source: authors' field survey, 2022

Data in Table 1 shows the respondents' opinions on the major causes of the conflicts between the oil companies and their host communities. It shows that 32% of the respondents mentioned environmental degradation by oil companies, 19.5% of the respondents mentioned unjust and inadequate allotment of community projects by the oil company, 21.2% of the respondents mentioned denying indigenes job opportunities in the oil companies, 15.1% of the respondents mentioned haphazardness or lack of speedy completion of community development projects by the oil companies and 12.2% of the respondents mentioned unrepentant youth militancy behaviours. The result shows that the majority of the respondents (32%) mentioned environmental degradation by oil companies as the major cause of conflict between the oil companies and their host communities in the areas studied. A close examination of the table revealed that the aggregate relative incidence of environmental degradation in the region is alarming and calls for attention.

Some of the precautionary measures, such as boiling water before drinking, are already entrenched in the day-to-day practices of people in the local areas around the oil and petrochemical installations. Some people interviewed stated that they always boil their drinking water because of fear of possible contamination from oil and gas activities. Also, there were reported cases of health problems across the community because of

environmental degradation by oil companies' mining activities, as was revealed by interviewees.

“My in-law just told me not to drink the water fetched from the river, that it will cause cancer, but since I don't know where else I will get water from, all I did was just boil the water and drink it.” **[Participant: IDI; male community member]**.

Another participant noted:

When we drink the water, we are afraid of the possible trouble it will bring to us, but I have no choice. Even we cannot trust the water from the vendors, and the government doesn't supply us with water **[Participant: IDI; male community member]**.

Another participant noted:

The people around here simply do not have the capacity to manage these things (pollution), they take water from other parts of the lake because the oil is not visible, and when they drink it, they fall sick . . . Our (community leadership) advice is for them not to even use the water for bathing until the company or government does something. **[Participant: IDI; female community member]**.

Another participant noted:

Pollution was a major problem in our community . . . it affects our rivers and fish . . . we could not fish nor collect water **[Participant: IDI; male community member]**.

In addition, the oil companies do not consider the indigenes of host communities in employment. One of the interviewees reported that “Government officials tend to influence company employment by introducing relatives or even influence big contracts to their personal favour.” **[Participant: IDI; male community member]**.

Another participant noted:

...oil companies give scholarships to community youths and give them contract jobs that expire in months. These youths still go back to the violence against the communities; the companies should engage the communities in meaningful employment and empowerment. **[Participant: IDI; male community member]**.

Another participant noted:

There were instances where we had our youth who graduated from university more than 10 years ago stay without having jobs. Unemployment is hitting very hard; this makes it very possible for people to be easily bought over and used by any group of people to cause any problem. Little employment opportunities could positively engage our youth and make them bread winners of their families, and this will have a magnified effect in maintaining peace in our communities **[Participant: IDI; male community member]**.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents on the causes of the conflict between host communities and oil companies

Cause of the conflict	Frequency	Percentages
Lack of sincerity in the pursuit of community development projects in host communities by the oil companies	108	12.6
Un-peaceful nature or culture of the host communities	16	1.9
Structural hardship inflicted on the host communities by the activities of the oil companies	670	77.9
Unjust and inadequate spread of community projects by oil companies	66	7.7
Total	860	100.0

Source: authors' field survey, 2022

As regards the major causes of the conflict between host communities and oil companies, data in Table 2 shows that 12.6% of the respondents mentioned lack of sincerity in the pursuit of community development projects in host communities by the oil companies, and 1.9% of the respondents mentioned the unpeaceful nature or culture of the host communities. Again, 77.9% of the respondents mentioned structural hardship inflicted on the host communities by the activities of the oil companies as the major cause of the conflict between host communities and oil companies, while 7.7% of the respondents mentioned that the unjust and inadequate spread of community projects by oil companies is the major cause of the conflict between host communities and oil companies. This implies that the majority of the respondents believe that structural hardship inflicted on the host communities by the activities of the oil companies is the major cause of the conflict between host communities and oil companies. Qualitative data corroborated this finding:

“... our farmlands and fishing rivers could no longer support commercial farming and fishing due to very heavy pollution; the only substitute we have is financial rewards, but the money is not flowing in terms of business support, cash payments, etc.; no hospitals with free medical services; and schools that are free. If these things are there, the tension will be reduced to the very minimum; the source of tension is caused by the fact that our people constantly wake up with poverty in the midst of perceived plenty. Such an environment in any human system cannot bring peace; it can only aggravate tension because every human being is geared up for survival, and when the survival is challenged, the people will surely rise against it.” **[Participant: IDI; female**

community member].

A male respondent complained that:

Once a spillage occurs, it spreads throughout the coastal communities. However, oil companies do not pay compensation to all the affected communities. Only a few communities may get compensation, and the rates of payment also differ. This has generated conflict between communities [**Participant: IDI; male community member**].

Discussion of Findings

Conflict is a complex phenomenon arising from human interactions. Sociologists, social psychologists, and scholars in other related fields have noted in their studies of human interactions that conflict is inevitable in human societies (Otite, 2001; Zartman, 1991; Folarin, 1998). Some scholars have even contended that conflict is a normal process of development in society (Park & Burgess, 1921). Hence, that there is conflict in the Niger Delta is not abnormal. Also, the conflicts in the Niger Delta have further underdeveloped the region, thereby contesting the assertion that it is a normal process of development. The society is perceived by conflict theorists as an arena where groups contend for power or benefits (Wallace & Wolf, 2006). Members of society may or may not be fully aware of this contention, depending on their level of involvement.

Findings of this study revealed that most respondents acknowledged that they had experienced major conflict in their areas. This suggests that there is a great link and relationship between corporate social responsibility and conflict. Undoubtedly, the unfriendly environmental operations of the multinational oil-producing companies in the area are major contributory factors to most of the conflicts. Consequently, genuine execution and involvement in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) activities can prevent and quell conflicts. This supports the findings of Banfield (2005), who rightly observed that conflict-prone organisations and their management symbolise a necessary part of a combined effort to get a more peaceful world. In other words, if the oil-producing companies in the Niger Delta honestly carry out well-planned corporate social responsibility activities with the involvement of members of the host communities, there will definitely be a cordial relationship with the host communities.

In addition, this will certainly affect changes or the result of conflicts in the local communities and society generally. It must be noted that positive Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) considerably reduces the negative

impact of business activities and consequently the likelihood of conflicts. It also increases the advantage of good neighbourliness and mitigates the negative results of business operations on the environment. Of course, society has and deserves the right to a healthy and decent environment. Society also has a right to a clean, safe, and healthy environment, and this is an undisputable human right. Oil-producing companies, therefore, have a responsibility to ensure this right to prevent conflict between them and the oil-producing areas where they operate.

From the foregoing discussion, it has been established that conflicts occur in the Niger Delta. It becomes pertinent, therefore, to explore the reasons behind the conflicts and their implications for the oil companies. Causes of conflict(s) by the participants are many; however, environmental degradation by oil companies and denying indigenes job opportunities in the oil companies appear to be the most cited causes of conflict between oil companies and their host communities. This finding agrees with Imobighe's (2004) assertions that conflict between the oil-producing communities and oil companies is traceable to the environmental degradation of the land and water on which the local communities depend for their sustenance. The findings of this study also corroborate Homan's (1958) assertion that people always evaluate different options available to them, so in choosing from the different options, they will be aggressive to the partner if they see the partnership as a problem that does not benefit them. The people consider environmental pollution and refusal to clean up the environment as problems that do not benefit them; this explains the community distrust and violence against the oil companies.

Similarly, the findings of this study support Oteh and Eze (2012) and Okonta (2006) in their respective studies on environmental issues that the crisis of underdevelopment and ecological devastation in the Niger Delta region have been the root causes of the crisis and that the oil-producing companies have not carried out enough corporate social responsibility programmes to placate the people. This has also been established by the findings of the UNEP (2011), which confirmed that ecological devastation of the Niger Delta area and its serious lack of infrastructure, such as electricity, potable water, and health facilities, are responsible for the volatile nature of the area. The report further stated that people in the area suffer from the enormous negative externalities engendered by oil extraction and production, including oil spills and gas flaring that will take about 30 years to remediate. Similar findings by Shaxson (2008) also acknowledged this fact. According to him, despite abundant oil wealth, the people have become more impoverished due to political marginalisation and excessive environmental damage, which have also

subjected the inhabitants to major health hazards.

Arguably, in any society, the government has the sole responsibility of ensuring development. Political campaigns are focused on a proposed development agenda, and electorates vote based on their judgement of the candidate with the best development plan. Though there have been arguments back and forth on the roles of businesses in the development process, the concept of social responsibility has come to be generally accepted. As a matter of fact, companies that neglect social responsibility risk facing conflicts. The implication of this for them was that for as long as the government continued to fail in its responsibilities in those communities, the oil companies would continue to be victims of transferred aggressions. It would be risky, therefore, for the companies to push the blame of underdevelopment to the government and hide behind it, because either way, they would serve as the “body shield” for the government by taking most of the attacks. Moreover, both the government and oil companies are culpable for the neglect of the oil-producing communities, but the oil companies are in more direct and physical contact with the communities and their expropriated inhabitants. Since the government is far away from the people, the oil communities vent their grievances on the oil companies.

Findings also indicated that the majority of the respondents mentioned that community development projects by oil companies are unjustly distributed. It could be inferred from the data that the distribution of benefits from petroleum production has been widely held to be inequitable against the interest and development of the oil-producing areas. The oil companies were accused of selectively implementing, or not implementing at all, the agreements reached with the communities. In a bid to force them to keep the agreements, the communities resorted to conflicts. The implication of this for the oil companies is bifurcated; firstly, the companies would lose their credibility among the people, and secondly, the violence against them might continue. The finding of this study is in consonance with Oviasuyi and Uwadiae (2009) on the dilemma of the Niger Delta region as oil-producing states of Nigeria. From their research, it was found that the distribution of benefits from petroleum production has been widely held to be inequitable against the interest and development of the oil-producing areas. They reported that today, the inhabitants of the Niger Delta village/community are left with nothing but damaged farmlands and polluted rivers with no electricity, potable drinking water or other basic social amenities. The locals in many of the oil-bearing communities claim to still live in primitive conditions akin to that of the Stone Age, side by side with the high-tech and modern facilities of the multinational community that they play host to.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that conflicts, basically, arise from structural hardship inflicted on the host communities by the activities of the oil companies that results in environmental degradation. It is sometimes because community development projects by oil companies are unjustly distributed in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. Therefore, there is a need to investigate the management strategies that will favour the host communities and the oil companies.

ecommendation

The oil companies should pay specific attention to the factors identified by the communities as being responsible for the occurrence of conflicts. For instance, companies should be mindful that the performance of the government in the state or country in which they operate would have immense implications on the perception they enjoy from their host communities. Hence, they should use their strategic economic position to encourage or pressurise the government into being responsible. Also, the oil companies should make efforts to spread their contributions to all the communities in the Niger Delta rather than paying too much attention to the restive ones. This is because some of the conflicts that occurred were due to the need for attention from some of the communities. Both the oil companies and the communities should constantly bear in mind the double-edged consequences of conflicts; hence, they must be avoided at all costs.

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